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SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION / EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the vision, objectives and actions for optimizing communication and public engagement of the GTCLC-NEG MSCA Project in maximizing social impact and for informing about the project itself and its funding by the European Union, complying with the Article 38 in the Grant Agreement. Therefore, the GTCLC-NEG strategy will not only be focused on explaining project outputs once achieved, but also on receiving feedback from stakeholders, applying a “Responsible Research and Innovation” (RRI) approach, as it has been since project inception, during project execution, both regarding its research and training objectives. The Communication Plan identifies the external audiences for GTCLC-NEG project and how to best engage with them, describing channels and materials to be used in each case, as well as specific activities. The Communication Plan does not intend to detail internal communication or dissemination in a strict sense (scientific/academic audience). Those aims will be reached mostly through a project management platform for internal communication, completed with mailing lists plus peer-re-viewed articles and presentations / posters at research conferences. The open science policy of GTCLC-NEG project has been already cleared in the **DMP. In this will be explained also the possible tools for the consortium members to share ongoing work and data.**

SECTION 2: VISION and TARGETS

The GTCLC-NEG project aims to contribute to the three goals set by the European Commissioner Carlos Moedas in 2016 for the EU research and innovation system: “Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World”. The vision for the GTCLC-NEG Communication Plan is how to best perform this task to achieve an Open Innovation and Open to the World project. The Individual Fellow (IF) is the fundamental actor in GTCLC-NEG Communication and outreach strategy.

The Communication Plan and the provision of training to support its execution has one ultimate goal: To increase the social impact of scientific work performed in the GTCLC-NEG process. **Social impact of research is defined** as to when published and disseminated research results lead to an improvement in relation to the goals agreed in our societies (through our political representatives).

The manifold of possible users to co-create with the GTCLC-NEG team future applications of the research must be aware of the existence of the project, the reasons to fund this research and its progress, so that they can apply obtained conclusions in the future as “sustainable” impact, well beyond the end of GTCLC-NEG in 2023. The plan starts by singling out this manifold of users and cocreators, to devise how to increase their awareness and engage them. Ultimately, the future career of GTCLC-NEG IF is one of the most important impacts in that sense, as detailed in the Career Development Plan (CDP).

2.1 TARGET AUDIENCES

The following groups have been identified as target audiences and key stakeholders to engage in the CAFE Communication process:

- Multiphase CFD Community: among them the most important subjects are listed in the following table.

Table 1: Main players to be contacted in the Multiphase modelling Community

Research Institute	Location
Monash University ¹ , Department of Chemical Engineering	Australia
University of Massachusetts Amherst, Multi-phase Flow Simulation Laboratory ²	USA
University of Texas at San Antonio (UTSA), Multiphase Flow Simulation Laboratory ³	USA
TU Eindhoven, Multi-scale Modelling of Multi-phase Flows ⁴	EU
Rice University, Particle Flow & Tribology LAB (PFTL) ⁵	US
NTNU, Department of Energy and Process Engineering, Multiphase Flow Laboratory ⁶	EU
University of Toronto, Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Multiphase Flow and Spray Systems Lab ⁷	Canada
NETL, MFIX Group ⁸	USA
Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf Computational Fluid Dynamics ⁹	EU

- Policy makers and public-sector managers such as infrastructure managers or emergency services, who can ultimately benefit from the application of carbon negative power generation technologies, which will result from the GTCLC-NEG project. Especially in the framework of the EU Climate Pact initiative and in the network of EU Climate Pact Ambassadors.
- Industry sectors such as energy, power generation, biofuels industry who are potential producers or users of carbon negative power generation technologies.

¹ https://www.mdpi.com/journal/processes/special_issues/computational_multiphase

² <https://www.umass.edu/multiphaseflow/>

³ <https://engineering.utsa.edu/mfsl/research/>

⁴ <https://www.tue.nl/en/research/research-groups/multi-scale-modelling-of-multi-phase-flows/>

⁵ <https://higgslab.org/index.html>

⁶ <https://www.ntnu.edu/ept/laboratories/multiphase>

⁷ <https://mussl.mie.utoronto.ca/>

⁸ <https://mfix.netl.doe.gov/>

⁹ <https://www.hzdr.de/db/!ContMan.Visi.Card?pUser=23&pNid=0>

- Citizenship: who should be more and more aware of the advantages of carbon negative technologies and of the fact that they can represent a possible solution to the Climate Change problem.
- School students and teachers, from primary to undergraduate. University managers in charge of PhD and Master programmes, who could benefit from the design and development of carbon negative technologies, to integrate some of the itinerary/syllabus into some more conventional Masters on Mechanical, Chemical and Energy Engineering.

SECTION 3: KEY MESSAGES

- Climate Change is the major global challenge of this century, with significant ramifications on human life. Unfortunately, it is unlikely that agreed climate targets can be met without removing CO₂ from the atmosphere. Negative Emissions Technologies are needed.
- The specific objective of the current project is thus to develop a carbon negative technology which can produce power and heat at low cost and which can be implemented rapidly. Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) of biofuels (such as: pyrolysis oils, biogas, solid biomass) can be such a process and is the basis of the project.
- Biomass absorbs CO₂ during growth and releases it when burnt; but if CO₂ is captured after combustion this will result in a net flow of carbon out of the atmosphere, i.e. Carbon Negative Technology by Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS). CLC is a form of unmixed combustion which uses an oxygen carrier to transfer oxygen from air to fuel and permits to have a pure flow of CO₂, which can be easily captured at a low cost. The aim of the project is to develop a multifuel CLC combustor which can be coupled with a Gas Turbine (GT).
- The combustor will work with new multi-metals oxides, to be used as oxygen carriers. These will be prepared and characterized with respect to their structural and microscopic properties, and finally tested in a pilot plant, based on circulating fluidized bed reactor. Particular attention will be focused on biofuels injection, combustor design and reaction kinetics modeling. An approach that will analyze first the oxygen carrier particle behavior, then the reactor performance will be adopted.
- Finally, the results will be used to scale up the process and couple the combustor with a gas turbine, designing an innovative power plant together with a leading industrial partner, which may have the capability to exploit the results.

It is expected that the project will generate important results, in order to implement an ambitious concept, needed for earth and society.

SECTION 4: CHANNELS. CONNECTING AUDIENCES AND MESSAGES

The following table links the essential GTCLC-NEG stakeholders (AUDIENCES) with the key messages more relevant for each of them and identifies the most appropriate communication channels to convey the messages to each audience. The next section details the appropriate tools and materials to reach the audiences through the expected channels.

Table 2: Key messages and target audience

AUDIENCES/ STAKEHOLDERS	WHO	CHANNELS	MESSAGES
CFD Multiphase community	Academics and Researchers and Engineers	Researchgate / Academia / Final Conferences. Other meetings and events.	Novel approaches beyond classic CFD modeling of PCLC plants Opportunities for modeling innovative combustors for gas turbines.
INDUSTRIAL SECTORS	Energy, Power, Gas Turbine producers, Fluidized Beds producers.	Training sessions Website / news, blogs, social networks. Events, Final conference.	New combustors to perform carbon negative emissions combustion.
POLICY MAKERS and PUBLIC SECTOR	Government and EC agencies/regulators; EU CLIMATE PACT services /Energy experts.	Poster, website, Events and workshops, Final conference.	Need for cooperation to transform GTCLC-NEG novel knowledge into feedback to design new carbon negative emissions power plants.
CITIZENSHIP/ SOCIETY AT LARGE		Website, social networks/video capsules, outreach /social networks interaction/blogs by students (events).	Restore level of CO2 concentration which are similar to those of pre-industrial times. Solve efficiently the Climate Change problem.

MEDIA	Journalists/science communication professionals in radio/TV /newspapers/online outlets.	Press releases; blog; Radio/TV presentations of the project and its results.	Similar messages to those of Society at large.
EDUCATION	School pupils / teachers; undergraduate and Master students and trainers.	Visits to schools, talks to undergraduates and master students; inviting master students to training events at GTCLC-NEG. Participation to the European Researchers Night and also to the EU initiative "Science is wonderful".	Innovative and interdisciplinary education to tackle climate change and its consequences; careers for curiosity driven researchers working on energy, mechanical and chemical engineering.

SECTION 5: COMMUNICATION TOOLS and MATERIALS

In order to convey the key messages to the target audiences (Table 1), the GTCLC-NEG Communication plan approach proposes the combined use of traditional tools with a communication strategy 2.0.

The straightforwardness of social networks to reach citizens and non-professionals will be put to better use with a careful, recognizably branded identity and the combined use of social networks for diverse use and audiences as well as more conventional materials such as posters and face-to-face events.

5.1 GTCLC-NEG Action Plan

5.1.1 Branded identity

The GTCLC-NEG logo (see figure 1) has been designed during project presentation in agreement with the supervisor Dr. Abad. This will be used in deliverables, presentation and report templates, which will be made available to project members. These steps are intended to consolidate project identity, highlight visibility and support recognizable communication.

Figure 1: Project logo

□ 5.1.2 Website

The GTCLC-NEG Project website (<https://pietrobartocci.wixsite.com/gtclc-neg>) was launched in early August 2020, during the project submission. It serves as a central portal into the project, providing information about the consortium, the Individual Fellow (IF), as well as research outputs. The website will be updated regularly and cater for diverse audiences, with sections such as the blog (which is accessible through the command “Newsletter”) addressing GTCLC-NEG topics and output for non-experts. On top of the GTCLC-NEG website, the diverse participants will post GTCLC-NEG-related content (based on news and updates posted on the project’s website and social network accounts; advertising video releases on YouTube) at their institutional websites. This will increase exposure and traffic to the GTCLC-NEG website itself as well as the visibility of the project and its results.

Figure 2: Website

□ 5.1.3 Blog

The GTCLC-NEG website will host an additional blog space with the IF as main contributing author. Blog entries will be the basis of content to be disseminated through the social networks, which can multiply visits to the articles. A project poster will be used annually for larger dissemination events, e.g., international and regional conferences. This (blog/outreach articles) will be part of the Career Development Plan (CDP).

□ 5.1.4 Social networks

Two social networks had been considered as essential for the GTCLC-NEG outreach plan in the proposal. They are confirmed during the meetings of the consortium: Twitter and YouTube. Accounts are up and running in both platforms.

o Twitter: The project username is: @gtclcneg2021 and the password is: GTCLC-NEG. The official twitter account will be used to disseminate news related to the project and consortium, such as advertising the results, as well as general content, the news and the topics discussed in the blog.

Figure 2: Twitter Website

o YouTube: The YouTube GTCLC-NEG channel will be used to disseminate video capsules to explain the project, the IF experience, team and results (see following point, Video Capsules), as well as recorded courses and sessions to maximize value and impact of the training organized in similar and overlapping topics.

Figure 3: You Tube Channel

□ 5.1.5 Video capsules and webinars

Video-capsules and webinars will be produced and released mainly communicating the main results of the project and its main impacts. A last video will show the final achievements in the final stage of the project.

5.2 CONVENTIONAL TOOLS

□ 5.2.1 Poster

A poster informing about the project and its main research objectives as well as the consortium has been designed for mass circulation at fairs, conferences, workshops (see figure 4). There will be hard-copies available from the Principal Investigator (on demand) and the pdf file will be distributed to the partners, so it can be used at events, as well as being available at the diverse participants headquarters and main sites.

The poster has been presented also at the 18th Multiphase Flow Conference & Short Course which was held online and was organized by the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, Computational Fluid Dynamics Department.

Batch fluidized bed model in MFIX software for simulation of chemical looping combustion

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Keywords: Chemical Looping, Combustion, Fluidized bed, Multiphase, Carbon Negative Technologies

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A CFD model implemented in MFIX software is integrated with detailed kinetic models to simulate a batch Fuel Reactor in the framework of the **Marie Curie project GTCLC-NEG**.

Bibliography: [1] A. Abad, T. Mattisson, A. Lyngfelt, M. Johansson, The use of iron oxide as oxygen carrier in a chemical-looping reactor, *Fuel*, Volume 86, Issues 7–8, 2007, Pages 1021–1035, [2] Zhong Ma, Shuai Zhang, Yonggang Lu, Activation Mechanism of Fe₂O₃-Al₂O₃ Oxygen Carrier in Chemical Looping Combustion, *Energy & Fuels* (IF3.605), Pub Date : 2020-11-19, DOI:10.1021/acs.energyfuels.0c02967; [3] A. Cabello, A. Abad, F. Garcia-Labiano, P. Gayán, L.F. de Diego, J. Adánez, Kinetic determination of a highly reactive impregnated Fe₂O₃/Al₂O₃ oxygen carrier for use in gas-fueled Chemical Looping Combustion, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, Volume 258, 2014, Pages 265–280.

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Figure 4: GTCLC-NEG project poster

□ 5.2.2 Press

The communication of the described face-to-face activities, like the International Conference on Chemical Looping, which will be held on September 2022 will be organized in press events addressing industrial sectors and policy makers to reach local and national newspapers, radio and TV. Some of the GTCLC-NEG research findings (papers, presentations at world-wide conferences, etc.) will also be considered for dissemination to larger audiences, reinforcing the use of the social networks and websites.

□ 5.2.3 EU initiatives: Researchers night and Science is Wonderful!

The project will be presented with specific interventions at the two most important science communication events organized by the EU:

1. The EU Researchers' night (see figure 5)
2. Science is wonderful (see figure 6).

Figure 5: The EU Researchers night 2021

Figure 6: The EU event Science is Wonderful!

SECTION 6: METRICS

In the following table, the diverse metrics to be used to check the effectiveness of the diverse channels and tools, as well as the social impact achieved by GTCLC-NEG project during its execution, are displayed:

Table 3: GTCLC-NEG project Metric Tools

TOOL	METRIC
WEB	Number of visits, number of visits to blogs, downloaded public deliverables and other materials.
SOCIAL NETWORKS: TWITTER	Number of followers, number of retweets, number of interactions.
SOCIAL NETWORKS: YOUTUBE (VIDEO CAPSULES; WEBINARS)	Number of views.
EVENTS FOR PROFESSIONALS; POLICY MAKERS	Number of hosted events, number of attendants. Registration form to provide information about the number and profile of attendants (academia/industry, background); use of a questionnaire as a survey of satisfaction regarding quality of the training and information provided.
OUTREACH EVENTS	Number of hosted events, number of visits to schools; number of school pupils attending; number of presentations
PRESS RELEASES	Number of hits in newspapers; downloaded news from newspapers from these hits; number of press appearances in radio/TV; number of press appearances as a consequence of the press release.